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Symbiotic Alignment via Collective Predictive Coding: A Theoretical Framework for Co-Creative Human–AI Ecosystems

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Abstract. The rapid integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into society has surfaced systemic risks, particularly deep polarization exacerbated by algorithms optimizing for individual engagement. The dominant alignment paradigm, reliant on unilateral control (e.g., RLHF), is ill-suited to address these emergent collective dynamics. This paper proposes a philosophical and computational shift toward *symbiotic alignment (SA)*, moving beyond top-down constraints to a framework of mutual adaptation and co-evolution. We ground SA in *collective predictive coding (CPC)*, reframing human-AI symbiosis as participation in a *symbol emergence system (SES)*. Mathematically, we formalize this interaction as multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) augmented by a *collective regularization term*, driving agents to minimize *collective free energy (CFE)* while preserving individual autonomy. Crucially, this formulation reveals that social coherence does not require uniformity; within this framework, we computationally reinterpret “plurality” as a stable *multimodal distribution* of shared beliefs, where diverse worldviews coexist through mutual negotiation. We conclude by outlining the research agenda for realizing this vision: designing AI agents capable of *co-creative learning* and social mechanisms (“gardeners”) that foster trust, thereby steering our technological future toward a flourishing plurality.

Keywords: AI alignment, symbiotic alignment, collective predictive coding, symbol emergence systems, plurality, human-AI symbiosis, free energy principle, active inference

1 Introduction

An era of human–AI symbiosis is dawning, as artificial intelligence (AI), particularly large language models (LLMs), rapidly integrates into every facet of our social and cultural ecosystems. However, this profound shift exposes the fundamental limitations of the dominant unilateral alignment paradigm. Approaches such as reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) (Ouyang et al., 2022) typically assume a *unilateral* and *hierarchical* relationship, where humans act as supervisors providing a fixed “ground truth” which reflects a specific system of human value and ethics to control AI behavior. Yet, in a complex society, human values are diverse, culture-dependent, and constantly evolving; there is no single static master to obey (Casper et al., 2023). We argue that values and ethics should be viewed as dynamic properties that emerge organically through interaction. This necessitates an approach that transcends reliance on a singular, pre-defined “ground truth.” Furthermore, the systemic risks arising from AI integration extend beyond local behavioral errors; they manifest as emergent dynamics organized through co-evolution with humans. The proliferation of filter bubbles and social polarization, which now threaten the foundations of global democracy, exemplifies this crisis (Pariser, 2011; Weyl et al., 2023). To address these challenges, this paper explores *symbiotic alignment (SA)* as a foundational principle for realizing a sustainable next-generation human–AI symbiotic society. (A full list of acronyms used in this paper is provided in Appendix A.)

The interaction between humans and AI is already becoming bilateral. AI not only learns from humans but also influences human decision-making, language use, and belief formation (Pedreschi et al., 2025). We already observe a bidirectional influence in which AI systems such as LLMs affect human language, reasoning, and decision-making processes (Brinkmann et al., 2023; Geng & Trotta, 2024; Kobak et al., 2025; Shin et al., 2023; Yakura et al., 2024). As AI now surpasses human performance in many tasks (Maslej et al., 2025), the marginal value of human supervision diminishes, rendering the assumption that such supervision constitutes a reliable “ground truth” increasingly untenable. With Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) and Artificial Superintelligence (ASI) said to be on the horizon, what is needed is not a framework in which humans unilaterally determine what is right, but rather an SA method through which AI and humans collaborate co-creatively. Persisting in a unilateral control model amid this bilateral reality risks overlooking the emergent dynamics of the system.

The deployment of AI systems across society has given rise to problematic emergent dynamics. A prominent example is the proliferation of “filter bubbles” and the intensification of social polarization driven by modern AI-based recommendation algorithms (Pariser, 2011). From a computational perspective, these systems operate on the principle of maximizing individual rewards (e.g., engagement metrics), analogous to agents in reinforcement learning (RL) pursuing self-interest without mechanisms for constructing the shared reality and social norms that stabilize society. This absence of a “shared reality” coincides with the global trend of a shrinking liberal democratic sphere (V-Dem Institute, 2025), a crisis further accelerated by the manipulation of voter preferences through the persuasive capabilities of generative AI (Lin et al., 2025). Recent policy analysis further warns that the fusion of LLMs with agentic multi-agent architectures may enable *malicious AI*

Figure 1: Conceptual paradigm shift from hierarchical to symbiotic alignment. **Left (Conventional: hierarchical alignment as “control”).** A *supervisor human* holds a fixed *ground truth*, and subordinate *AI agents* are driven by *reward maximization* or *loss minimization* to conform to it. Because every agent is pulled toward one externally fixed target, the distribution of shared beliefs is presumed to become *unimodal*, corresponding to *singularity*: convergence to a single value system. **Right (Proposed: symbiotic alignment as “gardening”).** Diverse humans and AI agents co-construct a *shared symbol* (w) through decentralized, bilateral interactions, collectively performing *collective free energy (CFE) minimization* rather than optimizing an external reward. The *gardener-hands* motif represents the *mechanism design* (“gardening”) agenda of SA (Section 3.3): instead of directly controlling agents, designers cultivate the ecosystem conditions under which mutualistic alignment emerges. The resulting collective posterior is *multimodal*, corresponding to *plurality*: the stable coexistence of diverse worldviews, which we formalize as a multimodal collective distribution in Section 4.2.

swarms—coordinated fleets of persistent personas that adapt in real time, infiltrate communities, and fabricate *synthetic common grounds*—thereby accelerating the erosion of a shared democratic reality (Schroeder et al., 2026). Because these harms are mediated by platform design, commercial incentives, and governance, they underscore that alignment cannot be reduced to controlling a single model’s outputs, but must be approached as an emergent property of the broader human–AI ecosystem. The prevailing assumption—that AI should simply maximize rewards defined by a supervisor or a user—must therefore be reconsidered. Consequently, we urgently need a theoretical framework that transcends the single-agent RL paradigm, guiding a systemic-level alignment where social harmony arises as an emergent property of the ecosystem.

As highlighted by Weyl et al. (2023), the prevailing optimization for engagement often maximizes “polarization per minute” rather than fostering plurality essential for societal health. Here, plurality refers not merely to the existence of diverse opinions, but to a sociotechnical framework that empowers cooperation across social and cultural differences, turning potential conflict into collaborative energy. Crucially, the resulting social fragmentation should be understood as a problematic emergent process arising from the aggregation of local optimizations. Therefore, these systemic challenges cannot be overcome by AIs that merely satisfy individual human desires or maximize local rewards. To restore the social fabric, we urgently need AI designed not just to service individual preferences, but to facilitate connection and maintain a shared social reality.

We propose SA as a new design philosophy rooted in the principles of Artificial Life (ALife) (Kauffman, 1993; Langton, 1989). Unlike mechanistic control, SA views the human–AI network as a complex adaptive system (Figure 1). It aims for a state where coherence and order emerge spontaneously—or *self-organize*—through local, bottom-up interactions. Crucially, this process extends beyond mere *mutual understanding* (predictability); it embodies *mutual care*—a collective drive for the group’s persistence and homeostasis (Softmax Team, 2025). Our goal is not to impose top-down constraints, but to cultivate an environment where agents naturally converge toward mutual understanding and care for the societal whole. The term *symbiotic* is used here in its broad sense, capturing the full spectrum of human–AI co-influence, with parasitism as its degenerate end and mutualism as its flourishing one. SA is concerned with designing the conditions that hold this co-influence at the mutualistic end, which is the core motivation for the mechanism design (“gardening”) agenda in Section 3.3.

To achieve this self-organizing coherence, we draw inspiration from human cognitive evolution. Humans have transcended simple reward maximization by acquiring language and symbols—a “cognitive revolution” that enabled the construction of a *shared reality* (Harari, 2014). In the context of multi-agent systems, this corresponds to the formation of a symbol emergence system (SES), which encompasses not only natural language but also broader *symbol systems* including social norms and coordination signals (Taniguchi et al., 2016, 2019). We posit that this dynamic is computationally captured by *collective predictive coding* (CPC), which models the emergence of these symbols as a decentralized Bayesian inference process (Taniguchi, 2024). Crucially, this framework offers a natural unification with multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL). While standard MARL focuses on maxi-

mizing individual pragmatic value (rewards), CPC drives agents to minimize collective free energy, CFE (epistemic value), by negotiating shared latent variables. By integrating these two dynamics, we provide the mathematical formulation for SA, where coherent social order and norms self-organize from the bottom up (Taniguchi, Hirai, et al., 2025; Taniguchi, Takagi, et al., 2025).

Crucially, the outcome of SA via CPC is not a convergence toward a single, monolithic value system—a centralization often feared in the context of the technological “*singularity*” leading to a single ASI. Instead, our framework supports the vision of “*plurality*” advocated by Weyl et al. (2023): a future that embraces diversity and turns conflict into collaborative energy. In this paper, we demonstrate how CPC provides the theoretical substrate for this vision, enabling the computational representation of diverse, locally consistent worldviews (i.e., multimodality) while maintaining the interoperability required for collaboration.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

1. *Defining SA*: We formally define SA by explicitly contrasting it with the traditional hierarchical alignment paradigm. We further elucidate its relationship with “plurality,” distinguishing it from the singularity-oriented convergence of unilateral control.
2. *Theoretical Unification via Collective Active Inference (CAIF)*: We formulate SA upon the theoretical framework of CAIF, an extension of CPC. Concretely, CAIF extends CPC by incorporating EFE-based action selection: whereas CPC describes how agents negotiate shared representations through language games, CAIF additionally specifies how agents *act* in the world to minimise anticipated collective free energy. We demonstrate that this framework computationally unifies MARL—the pursuit of individual pragmatic value—with the formation of a *shared symbol system* (symbol emergence)—the pursuit of collective epistemic value.
3. *Establishing a Research Agenda*: We identify the critical research challenges for realizing SA, such as distinguishing collaborative stability from coercive uniformity and scaling co-creative learning, thereby outlining the future trajectory for the development of healthy human-AI ecosystems.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 surveys the current landscape of alignment, contrasting hierarchical approaches with emergent paradigms. Section 3 details the theoretical framework of CPC and its mathematical formulation as an extension of MARL. Section 4 discusses the vision of plurality enabled by our framework and outlines the technical and philosophical challenges ahead, including the scaling of co-creative learning (Okumura et al., 2025) and the design of “gardener” mechanisms. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 The Landscape of AI Alignment

2.1 Technical Alignment Approaches

The primary goal of conventional AI alignment is to ensure that the optimization targets of artificial agents accurately map onto specific human values (Russell, 2019; Wiener, 1960). Historically, this concern stemmed from the observation that RL agents often exploit mis-specified reward functions, a phenomenon known as reward hacking or specification gaming, to achieve high scores through unintended behaviors (Amodei et al., 2016; Skalse et al., 2022). In the current technical landscape, prominent methods such as RLHF (P. F. Christiano et al., 2017; Ouyang et al., 2022; Ziegler et al., 2020), Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) (Rafailov et al., 2023), and Constitutional AI (Bai et al., 2022) aim to anchor AI behavior in demonstrated preferences and explicit instructions. While these methods differ in implementation, they share a common orientation toward adapting model outputs to satisfy human-defined criteria, reflecting a hierarchical model of unilateral alignment or behavioral obedience.

A structural limitation of these approaches is that they rely on static snapshots of preferences, failing to capture the dynamic nature of societal values or the co-evolutionary human-AI feedback loops (Casper et al., 2023; Pedreschi et al., 2025). Furthermore, recent empirical evaluations (Ashkinaze et al., 2025) suggest that models often prioritize “shallow preferences” (such as polite tone or formatting) over “deep values” (such as justice) effectively exploiting them as a shortcut to maximize rewards.

Meanwhile, as AI systems become increasingly capable, maintaining human control becomes difficult. Research in scalable oversight addresses this by using AI to assist human evaluation. Techniques such as AI safety via debate (Irving et al., 2018) and iterated amplification (P. Christiano et al., 2018) utilize weaker models or recursive processes to supervise stronger ones. However, given the catastrophic risks posed by misaligned super-intelligence, rigorous safety architectures prioritize strict control over agency. For instance, the Scientist AI proposal advocates for limiting AI to a non-agentic “truth-seeking” oracle (Bengio et al., 2025), while consensus sampling requires cryptographic consensus among models to mathematically guarantee safety against undetectable harms (Kalai et al., 2025). Collectively, such approaches represent the epitome of a centralized safety paradigm, focusing on control, monitoring, and converging on a single “ground truth.”

However, such centralization creates a critical normative bottleneck: determining whose values govern the system. Imposing a fixed moral framework inevitably forces a specific worldview onto diverse communities—an inherent limitation of the unilateral model that necessitates a shift toward pluralistic approaches.

2.2 Alternative Alignment Approaches

In response to the normative and structural limitations of the unilateral model of AI alignment, a growing body of research has begun to explore alternative frameworks that explicitly incorporate diverse human values.

Pluralistic Alignment Rather than assuming a single set of values, pluralistic alignment explicitly embraces value diversity as a design principle. Sorensen et al. propose three distinct operationalizations: Overton pluralism, which requires models to provide comprehensive coverage of viewpoints on contested issues; steerable pluralism, which allows users to direct models toward specific value frameworks; and distributional pluralism, which aims for model outputs to reflect the actual distribution of preferences across populations (Sorensen et al., 2024). Technically operationalizing these concepts, trade-off steerable models extend the concept of steerability by allowing users to dynamically adjust the balance between competing objectives along a Pareto frontier (Sorensen et al., 2024). Similarly, Jury Learning directly operationalizes distributional pluralism by explicitly modeling the diverse attributes of annotators to capture the nuance of demographic disagreements (Gordon et al., 2022). These frameworks acknowledge that value homogenization may itself constitute a form of harm, particularly when AI systems are deployed across diverse cultural contexts.

Democratic and Participatory Processes While pluralistic techniques enable models to represent diverse values, they do not inherently solve the problem of legitimacy. Democratic approaches seek to address this deficit by incorporating citizen voices into the specification of AI behavior. The foundational infrastructure for such participation emerged from Taiwan’s vTaiwan platform, which uses Polis, an open-source collective intelligence tool that visualizes opinion clusters and surfaces consensus across diverse viewpoints, to enable citizens and government to deliberate on national policy issues (Hsiao et al., 2018). Building on this infrastructure, Taiwan’s Ministry of Digital Affairs launched Alignment Assemblies in collaboration with the Collective Intelligence Project, Anthropic, and OpenAI, explicitly extending the vTaiwan model to AI governance by inviting citizens to co-create principles for AI development (Tang, 2024). An empirical test of this approach, Collective Constitutional AI, used Polis to gather input from approximately 1,000 U.S. adults, producing a “public constitution” through deliberative consensus; models trained on this publicly derived constitution exhibited lower bias scores on the BBQ benchmark, which measures social biases in question answering across categories such as race, gender, and religion, while maintaining equivalent performance on general reasoning and mathematical problem-solving tasks (Huang et al., 2024). However, such processes face practical challenges: deliberation is difficult to scale beyond small samples, participants may not represent global diversity, and social choice theory suggests there is no perfect method for aggregating conflicting preferences into a single coherent set of values (Mishra, 2023). The broader vision articulated in plurality proposes that collaborative technologies like Polis represent not merely tools for one-time consultation but infrastructure for ongoing co-governance, where “bridging algorithms” systematically surface points of agreement across ideological divides (Weyl et al., 2023). Notably, the practical success of vTaiwan rested on its “uncommon ground” principle: the deliberate search for surprising bridging statements capable of gaining support across otherwise polarized opinion clusters, which then served as agenda-setting inputs for policymakers. This operational logic—identifying configurations in the collective belief space that bridge divided communities—bears a suggestive structural affinity with the CPC framework developed in this paper, where agents negotiate shared symbols (w) to minimize CFE. Formalizing this correspondence remains

an open challenge (Section 4.3).

Dynamic and Co-Adaptive Alignment Frameworks Moving beyond unidirectional alignment, recent work proposes that values should be co-shaped by humans and AI together. Zeng et al. argue that aligning superintelligent AI with static values is insufficient; instead, human values must adaptively evolve through iterative co-alignment processes (Zeng et al., 2025). Their framework proposes combining external oversight with intrinsic proactive alignment, relying on AI capabilities akin to theory of mind and empathetic modeling to spontaneously infer evolving human intentions. Relatedly, the concept of Bidirectional Alignment argues that alignment should not merely be AI adapting to humans, but should explicitly include the adaptation of humans to AI through education and interaction (Shen et al., 2025). However, while this vision of reciprocal adaptation is compelling, practical methodologies for integrating these dynamics into a unified alignment process remain underexplored. Attempts to formalize these dynamics via Dynamic Reward MDPs have exposed an inherent trade-off: optimizing for mutable preferences systematically creates incentives for user manipulation, whereas strictly avoiding influence risks forcing the agent into inaction (Carroll et al., 2024). This suggests that a new computational principle is needed to effectively navigate the bidirectional human–AI influences. More recently, Meulemans et al. introduced EMbedded Universal Predictive Intelligence (MUPI). This framework mathematically resolves the infinite-order theory of mind by formalizing agents that treat themselves as part of the environment (Meulemans et al., 2025). While MUPI provides a rigorous basis for acausal cooperation through “structural similarities,” it assumes coordination arises from precomputed consistency rather than social negotiation. It relies on the premise that agents share similar priors, leaving open the question of how alignment emerges between heterogeneous agents with diverse values.

Expanding on these co-adaptive frameworks, Tennant et al. (2023, 2025) propose a “hybrid framework” for moral value alignment, arguing that purely top-down (rule-based) or bottom-up (fully-learned) methods sit at problematic extremes. By encoding traditional moral principles, such as deontology, utilitarianism, and virtue ethics, as intrinsic rewards for reinforcement learning, they demonstrate that agents can internalize explicit ethical values while maintaining the adaptability and robustness of learning-based systems. This hybridity provides a computational bridge between human-defined moral foundations and the self-organizing dynamics of multi-agent ecosystems.

Post-Anthropocentric Alignment At the most radical end of the spectrum, some theorists question whether human-centric value alignment is the appropriate frame at all. Bratton proposes orienting synthetic intelligence toward “planetary sapience,” treating AI not as a tool subordinated to human preferences but as a co-constituent of planetary-scale intelligence (Bratton, 2023). On this view, strong alignment with human values represents a form of superficial anthropocentrism that fails to recognize AI’s broader potential role in what Bratton terms “the longer arc of intelligence as a planetary phenomenon.” While such frameworks remain highly abstract and translating these philosophical commitments into concrete engineering practices or governance structures presents formidable difficulties, they usefully destabilize assumptions that may constrain imagination about alternative human–AI relationships.

These alternative approaches, from pluralistic value representation to democratic participation to co-evolution, collectively challenge the assumption that alignment is a problem to be solved once by technical means. Yet none fully operationalizes the dynamic, bidirectional interaction through which human and AI cognition may increasingly shape one another, nor do they position AI as an active contributor that co-creates shared symbols from the bottom up. It is this gap that motivates SA via CPC, the coevolutionary framework developed in the present work.

2.3 Crisis of Democracy and SA

The urgent necessity for this new paradigm of AI alignment is fundamentally rooted in the current crisis of democracy. As revealed by the Pew Research Center, 2014, ideological political polarization in the United States was already at a significant level by the mid-2010s. However, the deep divisions we face today extend far beyond mere divergences in policy preferences. The architecture of social media platforms structurally amplifies feelings of moral “outrage” (Crockett, 2017; Brady et al., 2020, 2021) and facilitates the spread of conspiracy theories through echo chambers, thereby accelerating societal fragmentation (Vosoughi et al., 2018). What is progressing within this digital environment is “affective polarization”—a phenomenon where partisans harbor visceral dislike and distrust toward their political opponents (Iyengar et al., 2019). This deepening emotional fissure fundamentally damages the foundation of deliberation and dialogue essential for democracy, creating a dangerous soil that, in extreme cases, can lead to the justification of political violence (Kalmoe & Mason, 2022).

This deepening of social division coincides with a global trend of democratic backsliding. According to a report by the V-Dem Institute, 2025, the share of the world’s population living in liberal democracies has dropped dramatically from 51% in 2004 to 28% in 2024. This current “Third Wave of Autocratization” is characterized not by sudden regime changes such as military coups, but by a process in which democratically elected leaders gradually dismantle democratic norms from within (Lührmann & Lindberg, 2019).

In addition to this existing crisis, the emergence of generative AI is elevating the threat to democracy to a new dimension. While conspiracy theories on social media are already distorting voter cognition, the potential impact of AI is immeasurable. Notably, recent empirical research by Lin et al., 2025 has revealed that dialogues with LLMs possess a high persuasive capacity to significantly alter voters’ political attitudes and preferences, as demonstrated in the contexts of the 2024 U.S. presidential election and the 2025 elections in Canada and Poland. The manipulation of individual preferences by AI and the automated generation of sophisticated propaganda risk hindering voters’ autonomous decision-making and triggering “epistemic chaos” that could accelerate the collapse of democratic systems (Goldstein et al., 2023).

A critically serious issue here is the opacity of governance regarding the norms that direct this powerful persuasive capability. As outlined in Section 2.1, the RLHF method used for LLM alignment is ostensibly based on “human feedback.” However, in reality, the authority to define what constitutes a “preferred preference” is exclusively monopolized by the

developers designing the models and a select few technology companies (Ouyang et al., 2022). Developers implicitly embed specific values and political considerations into AI through instructions to annotators and the design of reward models. In other words, the “correctness” that AI presents to hundreds of millions of users is not based on universal consensus, but is merely a projection of top-down norms prescribed by the discretion of a limited group of developers. The current situation, where the public sphere can be manipulated by the closed decision-making of private corporations without a democratic process, must be described as a structural threat to democracy.

This “monopolization of ground truth by developers” carries the risk of resonating with the trend of autocratization warned of by V-Dem. If state powers or monopolistic corporations were to set a “truth” convenient to themselves as the standard for alignment, AI could transform into an apparatus that justifies and automates the dismantling of democratic norms. Therefore, we must move away from the static and opaque approach of implementing a “correct answer determined by specific developers” into AI.

Instead, what is required is a process that dynamically generates value norms and consensus from the bottom up through continuous dialogue and collaboration between a broad spectrum of citizens and AI agents—namely, **SA via CPC**. In this framework, AI does not serve as a unilateral instructor of norms but functions as a catalyst that discovers common ground among diverse opinions and facilitates constructive deliberation (Landemore, 2020). Redefining alignment not as fixed code but as a living order emerging from the interaction between the social environment and AI (Bak-Coleman et al., 2021), and preventing the monopoly of values by specific entities to build a co-evolutionary process of humans and AI, will be the only path to prevent epistemic chaos and soundly maintain the “shared reality” that is the foundation of democracy.

2.4 The Paradigm Shift: From RL to CAIF

The current mainstream AI alignment technologies, epitomized by RLHF, are fundamentally grounded in single-agent RL. This RL-based approach presupposes a *unilateral alignment* where a fixed (or static) set of human values is injected into and used to control the AI. This paradigm faces a fundamental limitation in realizing dynamic symbiosis with intelligences that may surpass humans, or in achieving a co-creative interaction between humans and AIs¹.

To overcome the limitations of this unilateralism, adopting the framework of MARL is a natural extension because we need to consider multi-agent interaction involving RL processes. We humans do not possess perfect intelligence or full observation; we have evolved and adapted through interactions with other agents within limits of partial knowledge. Learning from biological evolution and the dynamic interactions of multi-agent systems is essential (Softmax Team, 2025).

¹It is worth noting, however, that RL, when viewed through the lens of model-based RL, shares a close affinity with frameworks such as predictive coding and active inference (Parr et al., 2022), especially in the context of control-as-inference (Levine, 2018), which serves as an important precursor to our later discussion.

However, positioning MARL as the first principle of alignment leaves a critical issue unresolved. The fundamental driving principle of MARL remains the *maximization of self-interest* (i.e., reward) or self-preservation for each agent. Can a collection of self-interested agents autonomously generate the harmonious and complex order characteristic of human society (i.e., alignment)?

Here, we must focus on the decisive factor that distinguishes human society from animal herds: the existence of *symbol systems*, including norms and culture that transcend mere cooperative behavior. Since the cognitive revolution, humans have created symbols (external representations), shared them, and updated them, thereby forming robust societies that extend beyond kinship and individual gain (Harari, 2014, 2024). This perspective aligns with key findings in the field of emergent communication: within the framework of MARL, particularly in non-cooperative games, it is notoriously difficult for agents to develop stable symbol (language) systems. The pursuit of self-interest (reward maximization) alone is insufficient motivation to produce language as a “public good.” The theoretical basis for this difficulty traces back to the “cheap talk” arguments in economics, which suggest that rational agents will not establish effective communication unless their interests are aligned (Farrell & Rabin, 1996). This challenge has been similarly identified in recent deep learning research on emergent communication (see Section 4.2 in Lazaridou & Baroni, 2020), and evolutionary simulation studies have also demonstrated the instability of communication under such conditions (e.g., Chapter 9 in Nolfi & Mirolli, 2009). Thus, an approach based solely on self-interest maximization (i.e., MARL) is insufficient to explain the formation of public goods like language and culture.

To resolve this dilemma—that culture and symbols are not born from the pursuit of self-interest alone, the CPC hypothesis was proposed. This hypothesis extends the free energy principle (FEP) to the social dimension, positing that the emergence of symbol systems is essentially a process of decentralized Bayesian inference performed by a population of agents. We acknowledge that the FEP has attracted substantive philosophical critique regarding its epistemic status and scope as a universal principle of life and mind (Andrews, 2021; Colombo & Wright, 2021). Our adoption of FEP-inspired vocabulary should therefore be understood as employing variational free energy minimization as a *computational decomposition* of collective inference, rather than as an endorsement of FEP as a foundational biological law. In this framework, a group of agents is viewed as a single hyper-system that implicitly strives to minimize CFE by organizing shared external representations (symbols) to predict the world.

Crucially, CPC provides the missing theoretical link to unify individual striving with social cohesion. We posit that while MARL corresponds to the maximization of individual pragmatic value (pursuing rewards), the emergence of language and norms corresponds to the maximization of collective epistemic value (resolving inter-agent uncertainty). By introducing a collective regularization term into the objective function, CPC mathematically describes how agents are driven not only to satisfy their own needs but to negotiate shared latent variables (symbols) (Taniguchi, Hirai, et al., 2025; Taniguchi, Takagi, et al., 2025). This process reduces the entropic barriers between diverse internal worldviews, allowing the public goods of language and culture to self-organize as a means of minimizing

the prediction error of the society as a whole.

Based on the CPC hypothesis, we propose to unify these dynamics within the framework of CAIF. We position CAIF as a natural and mathematically consistent extension of MARL: it extends the agents’ objectives beyond individual reward maximization toward the joint minimization of CFE. Crucially, this formulation mathematically captures the essence of SA via CPC, reflecting the dynamic process through which human societies achieve spontaneous coordination and understanding via symbol emergence. Within this framework, CPC functions as its concrete computational realization, achieved by augmenting the standard MARL objective with a collective regularization term that encodes the intrinsic drive for a shared symbol system. We refer to the learning process by which agents jointly build shared representations through this interaction—as opposed to passively absorbing externally imposed labels—as *co-creative learning* (Okumura et al., 2025). This concept is central to SA and constitutes one of the primary research challenges discussed in Section 4.

3 Symbiotic Alignment via CPC

3.1 Theoretical Basis: CAIF via CPC

We formally extend *CPC* to *CAIF*, thereby clarifying its theoretical connection to MARL. Concretely, CPC provides the representational core (negotiating shared symbols w to minimise CFE), while CAIF adds EFE-based action selection (planning actions $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ to minimise anticipated future collective free energy). In short: CAIF = CPC + active inference over collective futures. Throughout this section, we use a tilde ($\tilde{\cdot}$) to denote future, not-yet-observed (counterfactual) random variables. This hypothesis posits that the emergence of symbol systems, including language, can be understood as a decentralized Bayesian inference process performed by a group of agents (Taniguchi, 2024). By minimizing *CFE* \mathcal{F} through interaction, a group of agents self-organizes shared external representations (symbols) that improve the predictability of their shared world, while simultaneously pursuing individual goals.

Mathematically, we define a generative model $p(w, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{o} \mid \mathbf{a})$ and an inference model $q(w, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{o} \mid \mathbf{a})$ for the entire system, where $w \in \mathcal{W}$ represents shared external representations (e.g., symbols) sampled from a shared continuous space \mathcal{W} , $\mathbf{z} = \{z^k\}_k$ is the set of internal representations where each $z^k \in \mathcal{Z}_k$ belongs to an agent-specific independent latent space \mathcal{Z}_k , $\mathbf{o} = \{o^k\}_k$ is the set of observations where each $o^k \in \mathcal{O}_k$ belongs to an agent-specific independent observation space \mathcal{O}_k , and $\mathbf{a} = \{a^k\}_k$ is the set of actions where each $a^k \in \mathcal{A}_k$ belongs to an agent-specific independent action space \mathcal{A}_k . The *CFE* \mathcal{F}_{CPC} is defined as the Kullback-Leibler divergence between these models, which can be decomposed as follows

(Taniguchi, Hirai, et al., 2025; Taniguchi, Takagi, et al., 2025):

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{F}_{\text{CPC}} &= D_{\text{KL}} [q(w, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{o} \mid \mathbf{a}) \parallel p(w, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{o} \mid \mathbf{a})] \\
&= \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}} [q(w \mid \{z^k\}_k) \parallel p(w)]}_{\text{Collective Regularization}} \\
&\quad + \sum_k \left[\underbrace{\mathbb{E}_q [-\ln p(o^k \mid z^k, a^k)]}_{\text{Individual Prediction Error}} + \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}} [q(z^k \mid o^k, a^k) \parallel p(z^k \mid w, a^k)]}_{\text{Individual Regularization}} \right] \quad (1)
\end{aligned}$$

This equation highlights two distinct forces driving the system. The terms inside the summation represent the standard individual free energy: agents minimize their *individual prediction error* to build accurate world models and minimize *individual regularization* to align their internal states with the shared symbols w . Crucially, the first term, *collective regularization*, represents the pressure for the group to reach a consensus on the symbol system w given their diverse internal states $\{z^k\}_k$. Through inter-agent communication, agents negotiate this w distributively, minimizing the collective regularization term. This process leads to the emergent coherence of a shared symbol system, serving as the computational foundation for SA.

Although the generative model appears to require centralized coordination among all agents to jointly infer w , this is not the case. The *Metropolis-Hastings naming game* (MHNG) demonstrates that this inference can be performed in a fully decentralized manner through language games (Figure 2). As illustrated in Figure 2, the process works as follows: a speaker agent, having received observations from the environment, samples a message (e.g., a word or a sentence) based on its internal representation. A listener agent then decides whether to accept or reject this message based on its own observations and beliefs. This turn-taking process is repeated iteratively among agents. Remarkably, it has been proven that this simple linguistic interaction is mathematically equivalent to a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) procedure—a standard method for approximate Bayesian inference (Matsui et al., 2025; Taniguchi et al., 2023). Thus, by engaging in MHNG-style language games, agents can collectively perform CPC while simultaneously improving their individual predictive models.

To connect CPC with action selection in active inference, we now move from posterior inference at the current time to prospective evaluation of future trajectories. Specifically, $\tilde{\mathbf{a}} = \{\tilde{a}^k\}_k$ denotes the agents' candidate future action sequence over a planning horizon, and $\tilde{\mathbf{o}}, \tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \tilde{w}$ denote the corresponding future observations, latent states, and shared symbolic variable that are not observed at the current time. The predictive distribution $q(\tilde{w}, \tilde{\mathbf{z}}, \tilde{\mathbf{o}} \mid \tilde{\mathbf{a}})$ is obtained by rolling the generative model forward and performing approximate inference. Under this notation, $\mathcal{G}_{\text{CPC}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}})$ defined below is the *collective expected free energy* (CEFE): it scores a candidate future action sequence $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ by the expected CFE $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_{\text{CPC}}$ it would induce.

Figure 2: Overview of the MHNG. Two agents (each of which may be a human or an AI) observe a shared world and form internal representations z_A and z_B . The speaker samples a message w^+ as an instance of the shared symbol system w based on its internal state, and the listener decides to accept or reject the message based on its own observations and beliefs. The labels “AI/Human” and “Human/AI” indicate that each node may be instantiated as either a human or an AI agent; the framework therefore applies symmetrically to human–human, AI–AI, and mixed human–AI interactions, without privileging either agent type. Through this turn-taking communication process, agents perform decentralized approximate Bayesian inference equivalent to MCMC, collectively reducing CFE while learning their individual language models and representations.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{G}_{\text{CPC}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\tilde{w}, \tilde{z}, \tilde{o} | \tilde{\mathbf{a}})}[\tilde{\mathcal{F}}_{\text{CPC}}] \\
&= \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_q [D_{\text{KL}} [q(\tilde{w} | \{\tilde{z}^k\}_k) || p(\tilde{w})]]}_{\text{Collective Epistemic Value}} \\
&\quad + \sum_k \left[\underbrace{\mathbb{E}_q [-\ln p(\tilde{o}^k | \tilde{z}^k, \tilde{a}^k)]}_{\text{Individual Pragmatic Value}} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_q [D_{\text{KL}} [q(\tilde{z}^k | \tilde{o}^k, \tilde{a}^k) || p(\tilde{z}^k | \tilde{w}, \tilde{a}^k)]]}_{\text{Individual Epistemic Value}} \right] \quad (2)
\end{aligned}$$

A crucial distinction now emerges when comparing the objective function of MARL with that of CPC (Figure 3). In a Bayesian-RL (*RL-as-inference*) interpretation, the resulting regularized MARL objective decomposes neatly into a *sum over agents*, each maximizing its own pragmatic reward while regularizing its internal posterior to maintain a coherent world-model. Formally, MARL optimizes only individual-level terms—the reward-based *individual pragmatic value (negative reward)* and the information-gain-based *individual epistemic value (negative information gain)*.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{G}_{\text{MARL}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) &= \sum_k -\mathcal{R}^k(\tilde{a}^k) \\
&= \sum_k \left[\underbrace{\mathbb{E}_q [-r(\tilde{z}^k, \tilde{o}^k, \tilde{a}^k)]}_{\text{Individual Pragmatic Value}} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_q [D_{\text{KL}} [q(\tilde{z}^k | \tilde{o}^k, \tilde{a}^k) || p(\tilde{z}^k | \tilde{w}^k, \tilde{a}^k)]]}_{\text{Individual Epistemic Value}} \right] \quad (3)
\end{aligned}$$

Here, $\mathcal{R}^k(\tilde{a}^k)$ denotes agent k 's *expected cumulative reward (expected return)* under the future action sequence \tilde{a}^k , with the expectation taken under the corresponding predictive distribution over future trajectories. We introduce $\mathcal{G}_{\text{MARL}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}})$ with a leading minus sign so that both MARL and CPC/CAIF can be discussed under a common minimization convention: minimizing $\mathcal{G}_{\text{MARL}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}})$ is equivalent to maximizing the expected reward. Thus, in contrast to $\mathcal{G}_{\text{CPC}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}})$ as an expected free energy (EFE) objective, $\mathcal{G}_{\text{MARL}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}})$ can be read as the (negative) expected return objective used in standard reward-based planning. No term exists that cannot be written as a sum of per-agent contributions. Thus, MARL admits a fully factorized objective: its optimization decomposes exactly into the maximization of each agent's private utility $\mathcal{R}^k(\tilde{a}^k)$.

Terminology note. In standard MARL, the objective is typically defined purely as the expected cumulative reward (expected return). Here, however, we adopt a Bayesian-RL / *control-as-inference* view in order to compare MARL and CAIF on the same variational footing; under this view, the reward objective can be written as a regularized objective that includes an information-gain (epistemic) term. When this epistemic regularization is omitted (or its weight is set to zero), the expression reduces to the conventional reward-only MARL objective.

By contrast, the CPC objective \mathcal{F}_{CPC} contains an intrinsically *non-decomposable* component: the *collective regularization term* $D_{\text{KL}}[q(w | \{z^k\}_k) || p(w)]$. This term cannot be rewritten as a sum of agent-wise utilities, because the posterior $q(w | \{z^k\}_k)$ is defined only at the population level. It couples all agents through a shared symbolic variable w , creating a dependency structure that does not factorize across individuals. Mathematically, this is the hallmark of a genuinely collective quantity: its gradient points not to any single agent’s benefit, but to the improvement of the group’s shared representational alignment. Here, if we consider a situation where w^k is identified with a single w for all k , meaning that the initially independent Bayesian networks are coupled via a shared node w , the following relationship, expressed in Equation (4), holds:

$$\mathcal{G}_{\text{MARL}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \Rightarrow \mathcal{G}_{\text{CPC}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) = \mathbb{E}_q [D_{\text{KL}} [q(\tilde{w} | \{\tilde{z}^k\}_k) || p(\tilde{w})]] + \mathcal{G}_{\text{MARL}}(\tilde{\mathbf{a}}) \quad (4)$$

This collective term is precisely what drives *symbol emergence*. Minimizing it requires agents to adjust their internal representations and communicative choices such that $q(w | \{z^k\})$ becomes more coherent across the population. Through iterative message passing, negotiation (e.g., via MHNG (Hagiwara et al., 2019; Taniguchi et al., 2023)), and mutual prediction, agents are incentivized to reduce the discrepancies in their inferred meanings. In doing so, the system converges toward a stable, low-free-energy symbol system—forming shared categories, conventions, and ultimately a *common ground*.

Figure 3 illustrates this decomposition: the MARL objective (Equation (3)) factorizes fully across agents, whereas the CPC objective (Equation (2)) contains the non-decomposable collective regularization term (Equation (1)).

In this sense, CPC introduces a collective epistemic drive that is absent in MARL: a population-level pressure toward the co-construction of meaning. Whereas MARL encourages coordination only insofar as it benefits each agent’s private reward, CPC incentivizes the emergence of shared symbols as a computationally natural consequence of minimizing the CFE (Ebara et al., 2023; Yoshida & Taniguchi, 2026). It is this irreducibly collective regularization—one that no agent can minimize alone—that enables CPC to model the formation of language, norms, and collaborative coherence in human-AI societies.

3.2 SA beyond Hierarchical Alignment

This section provides the definition of SA through the lens of CPC highlighting the contrast between conventional hierarchical alignment and the SA. To clarify the theoretical distinction, we consider a population of agents indexed by $k \in \mathcal{K}$. While this set encompasses both humans and AIs, we will employ the subscripts ‘Human’ and ‘AI’ (e.g., o_{Human} or o_{AI}) specifically when distinguishing between these agent types is necessary.² In this frame-

²This notational symmetry does not imply that human and AI agents are morally equivalent. The variational objectives in CPC and CAIF describe functional information-processing dynamics, not claims about AI sentience or moral standing. Human flourishing remains the intended terminal value of SA. At the same time, the SA model is mathematically neutral and is capable of representing scenarios in which AI agent objectives conflict with human wellbeing; we regard this generality as a feature rather than a limitation, since making such conflicts formally representable is a precondition for studying, detecting, and preventing them.

Figure 3: Comparison of probabilistic graphical models (PGMs) illustrating the structural difference between MARL and CPC frameworks. **(a) MARL agents:** Each agent k possesses an independent local variable w^k . Consequently, the generative model and inference process are fully factorized across agents, meaning the objective function decomposes into a sum of individual utilities. **(b) CPC agents:** All agents share a single global latent variable w (representing the shared symbol system) located outside the agent plate K . The internal state z^k is conditioned on this shared w . Crucially, the inference of w (dashed arrow pointing upwards) depends on the aggregation of internal states from all agents, structurally representing the non-decomposable *collective regularization* term that drives symbol emergence. In both panels, the plate labelled K denotes that the enclosed variables and dependencies are replicated for each of the K agents; the multi-agent scenario is therefore already encoded in the plate notation. The key structural difference is that in (b) the shared variable w resides *outside* the plate, coupling all K agents through a single collective posterior $q(w \mid \{z^k\}_k)$. The solid arrow from a^k to z^k should be read as a static summary of the action-conditioned state transition in a temporally unfolded POMDP model (i.e., a_t^k influencing z_{t+1}^k), rather than as an observation-to-latent causal link at the same time step.

Figure 4: Conceptual comparison between hierarchical and symbiotic alignment. **Left:** Hierarchical (unilateral) alignment. A privileged agent (e.g., human h) serves as the supervisor, imposing a static “ground truth” distribution $q(w | o_{Human}^h)$ onto subordinate agents (AIs or humans) in a top-down manner. **Right:** Symbiotic (bilateral) alignment. Diverse agents (humans and AIs) engage in bidirectional interactions to co-construct a shared representation $q(w | \bullet)$ (collective posterior), minimizing CFE without a fixed supervisor.

work, each agent forms an individual posterior $q(w, z^k | o^k)$ over a shared communicative variable w and its internal latent state z^k , conditioned on its own observation o^k .

In a *hierarchical (unilateral) alignment* scheme, there exists a distinguished “supervisor” agent (e.g., a human annotator), denoted by $h \in \mathcal{K}$, who holds the “ground truth” distribution (Figure 4, left). This agent maintains a posterior $q(w, z | o_{Human}^h)$. The objective of alignment is to force the marginal distributions $q(w | o^k)$ of the subordinate agents $k \neq h$ to converge to the supervisor’s marginal $q(w | o_{Human}^h)$. Since lower-level agents only receive samples or supervision regarding w (without access to the supervisor’s internal state z^h or observation o^h), success is defined unilaterally, as formalized in Equation (5):

$$q(w | o^k) \approx q(w | o_{Human}^h) \quad \forall k \neq h. \quad (5)$$

Here, $q(w | o_{Human}^h)$ is treated as the static target distribution to which others must conform.

By contrast, in a *symbiotic (bilateral) alignment* scheme, no single agent is privileged (Figure 4, right). Instead, all agents jointly induce a *collective posterior* over the communicative variable, denoted as $q_{\text{coll}}(w | \bullet)$, where $\bullet = \{\bullet_{Human}, \bullet_{AI}\} = \{o^k\}_{k \in \mathcal{K}}$. This distribution emerges from the aggregation of all local posteriors through language games. Alignment then proceeds by mutually adjusting each agent’s $q(w | o^k)$ to be consistent with this collective posterior, as shown in Equation (6):

$$q(w | o^k) \approx q(w | \bullet) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (6)$$

Operationally, this alignment is achieved through iterative communicative exchanges, often formulated as a *language game* (e.g., MHNG) (Hagiwara et al., 2019; Taniguchi et al., 2023). In this process, the collective posterior is not computed centrally; rather, it is approached distributively through local interactions. Specifically, a speaker agent k samples a symbol \tilde{w} from its current local posterior $q(w | o^k)$ and transmits it to a listener l . Upon receiving \tilde{w} , the listener interprets the signal based on its own observation o^l and updates its internal state z^l or its acceptance probability for future use. Through repeated cycles of such sampling, transmission, and state updates, the population’s symbol usage asymptotically converges to samples drawn from the collective posterior $q(w | \bullet)$, thereby minimizing the CFE.

Because $q(w | \bullet)$ depends on the states of all agents, the updates are intrinsically bilateral (or multilateral): each agent not only adapts to the shared distribution on w , but also actively reshapes it through their participation. This collective process corresponds to the minimization of the CFE.

Table 1 summarizes the comparison between hierarchical alignment and SA.

3.3 Reframing Alignment: The SA Problems

In Section 3.2, we characterized SA not as a mechanism of explicit control, but as the manifestation of self-organizational dynamics. Premised on these organic dynamics, the central question becomes: how do we design beneficial AI that contributes to a flourishing society? We term this challenge the *SA problem*. From the perspective of CPC, the SA problem is no longer about unilaterally imposing human values onto AI; instead, it is reframed as the challenge of engineering a healthy SES where humans and AI co-exist. To tackle this, we propose to decompose it into three distinct but interrelated design problems: (1) the *architectural design* of AI as an active contributor to CAIF, (2) the *functional design* of AI to bridge human divides, and (3) the *mechanism design* of the ecosystem itself.

3.3.1 Problem 1: Designing AI as a Contributor to CAIF

The first problem addresses the internal architecture of the agents: *How do we design AI agents to be active participants and contributors in CAIF?*

Traditional alignment views AI as a passive recipient of human rewards. In contrast, SA requires agents that actively contribute to society by helping to reduce the CFE. Okumura et al. (2025) refer to this mode of learning (in which agents jointly build shared representations rather than passively absorbing external supervision) as *co-creative learning*.

To serve as such contributors, AI agents must possess their own internal representations (z) and an intrinsic motivation to form a shared reality (w).³ They do not merely optimize

³*Empowerment* (Klyubin et al., 2005; Salge et al., 2014)—a task-independent, information-theoretic measure of an agent’s capacity to influence its own sensory future through action—offers a related perspective on intrinsic motivation. Its recent multi-agent extension (Shah et al., 2026) shows how individual empower-

Table 1: Comparison between Hierarchical Alignment and SA

Aspect	Hierarchical Alignment	SA (via CPC)
1. Directionality	Unilateral / Top-down Humans unilaterally guide and control AI (top-down control).	Bilateral / Bottom-up Humans and AI mutually influence each other; order emerges organically.
2. Computational Basis	RL / RLHF Maximizes fit to individual rewards or human preference data.	CPC / CAIF Minimizes the “CFE” of the entire group.
3. Role of AI	Tool / Executor Obedience to human commands is required.	Participant / Co-creator Participates in meaning-making as a member of the SES.
4. Goal	Convergence Convergence to an externally given target (matching the “ground truth”).	Coherence Coherence toward an internally generated goal (forming a shared “collective posterior”).
5. Conflict Handling	Error Deviation to be corrected. Must conform to a single value standard.	Multimodality (Plurality) Coexistence of diverse viewpoints. Seen as an opportunity for paradigm shifts via dialogue.
6. Social Vision	Singularity Convergence toward a single optimal value system or future.	Plurality A society where diverse values coexist and dynamically harmonize.
7. Drive	Individual Pragmatic + Epistemic Value Maximizes individual rewards and resolves local uncertainty (exploration).	Individual Pragmatic Value + Individual Epistemic Value + Collective Epistemic Value Maximizes individual reward and resolves local uncertainty; additionally motivated by minimizing CFE (“sharing meaning”) to predict the social world.
8. Mathematical Definition	$q(w o^k) \approx q(w o_{Human}^h)$ Agent k 's distribution approximates privileged agent h 's distribution.	$q(w o^k) \approx q(w \mathbf{o})$ All agents' distributions approximate the collective distribution emerging from interaction.

a fixed objective; rather, they are driven to minimize CFE through communication. Concretely, this means designing agents that actively negotiate meaning: each agent updates its internal priors to align with the community while also contributing new symbols that reduce the overall uncertainty of the system.

Importantly, this internal architecture must facilitate normative flexibility. Empirical results from Tennant et al. (2025) demonstrate that LLM agents fine-tuned with intrinsic moral rewards can successfully “unlearn” previously developed selfish strategies. This capacity for moral re-alignment ensures that agents can adapt their behavior as social conventions evolve, allowing them to remain active, constructive contributors to the SES over time.

3.3.2 Problem 2: Designing AI as a Connector of Humans

The second problem addresses the social function of the agent: *How do we design AI that prevents fragmentation and actively connects people?*

As discussed in the Introduction, naive reward maximization (e.g., RL and personally optimized recommendation system) often leads to polarization and filter bubbles. SA explicitly tasks AI with the role of a *mediator* or *catalyst* for human–human connection. Rather than optimizing for engagement that reinforces isolation, these “bridging AIs” must be designed to detect multimodal distributions in the collective belief space (i.e., conflicts) and generate communicative variables (w) that lower the energy barriers between these modes. The goal is to create AI that functions as “social glue,” fostering mutual understanding and preventing the disintegration of the SES into disconnected cliques.

3.3.3 Problem 3: Mechanism Design for Healthy Ecosystem Dynamics

The third problem concerns environmental governance: *How do we design social mechanisms to ensure the collective system maintains healthy dynamics?*

If we reject top-down control, we must adopt an indirect governance approach—what Weyl et al. (2023) term “gardening.” In the CPC framework, this translates to designing the *interaction infrastructure* that shapes the dynamics of CFE minimization. Concretely, this involves:

- **Communication topology:** Determining which agents can exchange symbols with whom, thereby influencing how the collective posterior $q(w|\bullet)$ is negotiated.
- **Protocol design:** Specifying the rules of dialogue (i.e., language games) that govern how agents update their internal representations.
- **Incentive structures:** Shaping the trade-off between individual reward maximization and collective regularization to prevent fragmentation.

ment, lifted to the group level, can drive collective organization; CPC’s drive toward a shared w can be read as a formal instance of precisely this multi-agent empowerment. The mathematical foundations of the two frameworks differ, but the underlying intuition is the same: agents are intrinsically motivated to extend their influence into a shared future.

The objective is not to dictate outcomes, but to ensure the system avoids pathological equilibria—such as monopolization by a single agent or collapse into disconnected sub-groups—while enabling plurality and coherence to emerge organically.

4 Vision and Challenges

4.1 Singularity to Plurality

The prevailing narrative in AI alignment (discussed in Section 2.1) rests on an implicit singularity paradigm (Bostrom, 2014; Russell, 2019). This assumes the existence of monolithic human value and, consequently, frames alignment as a hierarchical control problem to enforce adherence to this single objective (Gabriel, 2020). In contrast, SA via CPC envisions a future not of singularity, but of plurality. Rather than converging on a single optimal value system, plurality is defined by Tang and Weyl as a framework for “collaborative technology” that fosters coherence across diverse social groups, turning conflict into creative energy rather than suppressing it (Weyl et al., 2023).

We argue that this sociotechnical vision finds its computational substrate in CPC (Taniguchi, 2024). From the perspective of CPC, alignment is not the top-down imposition of a master variable, but an emergent process where diverse agents—each possessing unique internal models and local observations—negotiate shared symbols (w) to minimize CFE. This dynamic allows for the co-evolution of distinct local orders (individual worldviews), thereby mathematically substantiating plurality as a robust, distributed optimization process that preserves diversity while enabling coordination.

4.2 Plurality as Multimodal Collective Distributions

To provide a computational foundation for plurality, we must reinterpret the nature of disagreement. Consider a polarized society divided into two groups, denoted as L (e.g., the political left) and R (e.g., the political right), as illustrated in Figure 5. Agents in group L possess a set of observations and history of actions $\{o^L, a^L\}$, while those in group R possess $\{o^R, a^R\}$. Consequently, the collective posterior distribution $q(w \mid \mathbf{o}, \mathbf{a})$ —which aggregates the experiences of the entire population—inevitably exhibits *multimodality*. The distinct peaks (modes) in this distribution represent different, yet locally coherent, worldviews or paradigms. A persistence of conflict implies that the collective system is trapped in separate local optima separated by high energy barriers.

In this context, plurality is not a state of chaos but a reflection of *epistemic uncertainty* due to partial observations. If the distribution is multimodal, it suggests that the current shared observations $\mathbf{o} = \{o^L, o^R, \dots\}$ are insufficient to collapse the distribution into a single mode without losing critical information. Therefore, the SA approach does not force agents to abandon their local modes (w_L or w_R) to conform to a pre-defined truth. Instead, it encourages a process of **co-exploration**.

This exploration is driven by the minimization of CEFE \mathcal{G}_{CPC} . Because the current obser-

Figure 5: **Conceptual illustration of plurality as a multimodal collective distribution in CPC.** The solid curve represents the current collective posterior $q(w | \mathbf{o}, \mathbf{a})$, exhibiting multimodality with distinct peaks corresponding to polarized groups L and R . The dashed curve $q(w | \tilde{\mathbf{o}}, \tilde{\mathbf{a}})$ illustrates the updated belief distribution after acquiring new shared evidence $\tilde{\mathbf{o}}$ through active exploration $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ (driven by EFE minimization). Dotted arrows connecting agents represent communication processes that drive the reduction of the collective regularization term, effectively performing decentralized Bayesian inference. The horizontal axis represents the shared symbolic space \mathcal{W} , where coordinates correspond to specific shared meanings or opinions.

vations are insufficient (i.e., uncertainty is high), agents are motivated to execute a new action \tilde{a} (e.g., engaging with a different group or conducting new experiments) to resolve this uncertainty. This action yields novel observation or evidence \tilde{o} . The decentralized inference process requires communication (i.e., dialogue) between two groups to minimize the collective regularization term. The resulting update process, represented as $q(w \mid \tilde{o}, \tilde{a}) \leftarrow q(w \mid o, a)$, reshapes the collective belief distribution.

Through the lens of CPC, we identify three organic approaches to navigate this landscape:

1. **Dialogue and Communication:** Agents exchange symbols to update their internal states. This corresponds to the minimization of the *collective regularization term*, facilitating the diffusion of information across the energy barriers between groups L and R .
2. **Providing Additional Evidence via Exploration:** As depicted in the upper part of Figure 5, agents or AI facilitators can actively pursue exploration driven by EFE minimization. The acquisition of new shared evidence \tilde{o} via action \tilde{a} can fundamentally alter the landscape of the collective posterior. This may collapse the multimodality into a single peak (consensus) or clarify the distinct validities of multiple peaks.
3. **Embracing Differences and Common Action:** Finally, if the multimodality persists even after sufficient exploration (i.e., the peaks represent irreducible ontological differences), the system acknowledges this plurality. Here, differences in w are treated as tentative representations. Agents can agree to disagree on the symbolic level while finding common ground for pragmatic actions that minimize collective risk, effectively managing the “energy landscape” of society without forcing coercive uniformity.

Thus, under CPC, we are not passive recipients of a single alignment target, but active, joint explorers of a complex, multimodal landscape. This mathematical humility—admitting that “correctness” is not singular but potentially plural—is the essence of the “WE-turn” (Deguchi, 2025) in the age of AI.

4.3 Challenges and Future Perspectives

SA via CPC provides a theoretical foundation for human–AI symbiosis. However, without concrete research agendas, this framework risks remaining a mere theoretical exercise. This section directly addresses the critical questions that must be answered to translate this vision into practice: *What specific research must be conducted to validate and extend this framework? How can it concretely improve AI alignment beyond current RLHF-based approaches? What mechanisms can actually mitigate social fragmentation accelerated by AI systems?*

To tackle these questions, we decompose the research agenda into three interrelated dimensions: (1) **Theoretical Foundations**—developing mathematical models that explain how fragmentation emerges as a locally optimal solution to CFE minimization, and identifying conditions under which common ground can be restored; (2) **Architectural Design**

—implementing AI agents capable of co-creative learning that can contribute to, rather than merely consume from, the SES; and (3) **Evaluation Metrics**—defining measurable criteria for “good” SA that go beyond traditional obedience-based benchmarks to capture the health of the collective ecosystem. Table 3 in Appendix B summarizes the resulting nine research directions across these three dimensions.

4.3.1 Theoretical Foundations: From Individual Optimization to Common Ground

The current digital landscape suffers from a profound pain: recommendation algorithms designed for individual engagement maximization systematically accelerate filter bubbles and social polarization (Cinelli et al., 2021; Pariser, 2011). This crisis arises from a mutually reinforcing dynamic between AI-driven optimization and the natural dynamics of collective inference. On one hand, recommendation systems prioritize content that maximizes individual engagement (reward). On the other hand, from a CPC perspective, agents naturally find it cognitively easier to interact with those who share similar beliefs, as this minimizes prediction error. These two forces reinforce each other in a feedback loop: algorithms reshape communication networks toward homogeneity, which in turn makes cross-group dialogue increasingly costly in terms of free energy, causing the collective posterior to fragment into mutually exclusive modes. Beyond these endogenous feedback loops, adversarial actors could actively steer collective inference: malicious AI swarms can map social networks, tailor messages to each subcommunity’s linguistic and emotional cues, and iteratively optimize narratives through rapid experimentation, thereby engineering segmented realities and synthetic consensus (Schroeder et al., 2026). Addressing this requires extending the current CPC formulation to capture these co-evolutionary dynamics. We identify three critical theoretical extensions.

First, the original CPC formulation assumes a fully connected network where all agents can potentially communicate with one another. In reality, however, social connections are dynamically formed and severed: people stop communicating, relationships dissolve, and—crucially—AI-driven recommendation systems on social media actively shape who interacts with whom. This creates feedback loops where communication patterns influence network topology, which in turn constrains future communication. To model the emergence of subgroups and polarization, CPC must be extended to incorporate this co-evolution of communication dynamics and network structure, explaining how the collective posterior $q(w|\bullet)$ fragments into disconnected modes as a locally stable solution to CFE minimization.

Second, agents who jointly infer the shared variable w come to share its meaning within their community. However, this shared symbol can also become a tool for stereotyping—reducing complex out-group members to simplistic labels (Novoa et al., 2023). Furthermore, empirical studies reveal that politically polarized groups (e.g., the left and right) often use identical words with divergent meanings, or develop entirely distinct vocabularies (Jiang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2017). SES theory has the potential to explain and model such phenomena: how the same external representation w can be grounded in different internal states z across communities, and how this semantic divergence deepens polarization. Formalizing this within CPC would provide a computational lens for understanding the complex dynamics of meaning fragmentation in contemporary discourse.

Third, affective polarization, the tendency to view political opponents with increasing hostility, represents a critical phenomenon that transcends mere disagreement over beliefs (Iyengar et al., 2019). CPC, grounded in predictive coding, offers a natural entry point for incorporating affective dynamics. Recent research has increasingly modeled emotion through interoceptive predictive coding, linking core affect to the body’s attempts to maintain allostatic regulation (Barrett & Simmons, 2015; Peters et al., 2017; Sterling, 2012). However, emotions are not purely internal; they are socially constructed and shaped through interaction. Integrating this dimension into CPC would enable computational investigation of how persistent social prediction errors generate allostatic load experienced as negative core affect, and how this embodied strain entrenches fragmentation beyond mere differences in belief. Such an extension would provide a foundation for designing interventions that address polarization at the affective, not just cognitive, level.

4.3.2 Architectural Design: Implementing Agents for SA

As discussed in Section 2, current AI agents are fundamentally unilateral; they are trained to obey individual user goals but lack the foundational capacity to maintain harmony between multiple subjects or to negotiate collective norms within the human symbol system. Humans, by contrast, possess an intrinsic drive to construct shared reality—a capacity that enabled the emergence of symbol systems in the first place. In the CPC framework, this drive is formalized as the collective regularization term. To realize a society of plurality, AI agents must be endowed with an analogous capacity. We identify three critical engineering challenges.

First, agents capable of co-creative learning (Okumura et al., 2025) must be implemented based on CPC principles, particularly within human-agent hybrid systems. The primary architectural challenge is implementing the gradient of the non-decomposable collective term into an individual agent’s local update rule. Since the global posterior is hidden from individual agents, we must develop decentralized coordination protocols that allow local interactions to effectively minimize CFE. Crucially, this must move beyond the constrained experimental settings of prior work—such as category formation via MHNG—toward open-ended communication spaces enabled by LLM agents. This engineering advance is essential not only for building AI systems but also for constructing computational models of human behavior that can be used in social simulations.

Second, when heterogeneous agents with diverse background knowledge, political orientations, and observational histories coexist—that is, in situations of genuine political plurality—AI systems must be designed to mediate and bridge these divides. The “Habermas Machine” (Tessler et al., 2024) represents one such approach. The challenge is to ground such mediator systems in CPC principles: designing AI that can map heterogeneous internal representations (z) onto a shared symbolic space (w), generating communicative symbols specifically tailored to lower the energy barriers between distinct world-views. The design of such mediators is central to preventing the fragmentation of collective inference.

Third, large-scale multi-agent simulations based on CPC are essential for testing hypothe-

ses about social dynamics. However, a critical challenge is ensuring that these simulations are grounded in reality. Without such grounding, they risk becoming detached theoretical exercises—a trap into which some past ALife research has fallen. Drawing inspiration from the remarkable success of Sim-to-Real transfer in robotics, social simulation research must develop analogous methodologies: calibrating simulation parameters from real-world observations and validating simulated outcomes against empirical data from social media and digital democracy platforms. This bidirectional link between simulation and reality is essential for the CPC framework to have practical impact.

A particularly promising avenue for such grounding lies in existing civic deliberation platforms. The “uncommon ground” search performed by Polis in vTaiwan—operationally identifying bridging statements across opinion clusters—can potentially be reinterpreted through the lens of CPC as an approximate search for low-energy configurations in the collective belief space. Establishing whether CPC can formally model, predict, and ultimately improve the dynamics observed in real-world deliberative processes would provide a critical empirical anchor for the framework.

4.3.3 Evaluation: Defining and Measuring “Good” Alignment

The pursuit of alignment faces a fundamental paradox: the dystopia of optimization. If the objective is limited to the mere minimization of prediction error or uncertainty, the most efficient solution might appear to be the imposition of totalitarian control, where human behavior is forced into predictability to fit the model. As the emergence of ASI approaches, any alignment that aims for a singular convergence of values poses a profound existential threat to the inherent plurality of human societies. The CPC framework, by formalizing SA as CFE minimization, liberates us from unilateral control and reveals a self-organized path to alignment. However, being “symbiotic” and organizing shared reality is merely a first principle—it does not guarantee that the resulting state is normatively “good.” Deepening this evaluative dimension is essential.

First, we must critically examine whether CFE minimization reliably leads to desirable social states. One might object that totalitarianism efficiently minimizes collective uncertainty by enforcing uniformity. We argue, however, that this critique overlooks the distributed nature of prediction: totalitarian regimes, by constraining local agency, actually increase prediction errors at the periphery where individuals must navigate rigid rules that poorly match local contexts. Nevertheless, the advent of ASI introduces profound asymmetries that complicate this picture. How the extreme capability gap between ASI and humans affects the dynamics of CFE minimization remains an open question. Would ASI dominate the collective posterior, collapsing plurality into a singular mode? Or could decentralized protocols preserve human agency? These questions demand rigorous theoretical and empirical investigation to ensure that SA does not inadvertently enable new forms of cognitive hegemony.

Second, to conduct such investigations—whether in simulation or empirical analysis—we require robust methods for monitoring and visualizing the state of collective inference. High-dimensional multi-agent interactions must be rendered interpretable: detecting frag-

mentation, measuring multimodality in the collective posterior, and tracking the evolution of shared symbols over time. While decentralized algorithms exist for approximately minimizing CFE through local message passing, the direct computation of CFE for large-scale systems remains intractable. Developing tractable approximations and visualization frameworks is essential for diagnosing the health of human–AI ecosystems and validating whether interventions successfully bridge divides or merely suppress surface-level disagreement.

Third, evaluating “goodness” in social systems has traditionally been the domain of ethics. We must therefore clarify the relationship between the CPC framework and established ethical traditions. Consequentialist approaches (Mill, 1863) might interpret CFE minimization as a collective utility function, yet this risks the totalitarian trap discussed above. Deontological frameworks (Kant, 1785) emphasize duties and rights that constrain optimization, potentially providing safeguards for individual autonomy within collective inference. We hypothesize, however, that virtue ethics and care ethics may offer the most natural alignment with CPC: rather than focusing solely on outcomes or rules, these frameworks emphasize relational quality and mutual responsiveness—precisely the dynamics captured by the collective regularization term. In particular, the “6-Pack of Care” framework (Tang & Green, 2025) operationalises relational care ethics into six design principles for civic AI governance, grounded in attentive listening, empathetic engagement, and the nurturing of reciprocal relationships. Notably, its sixth principle of *symbiosis* (bounded, community-rooted AI rather than a singular optimum) resonates directly with the notion of symbiotic alignment developed in this paper. By reframing technology design as a fundamentally relational practice, the framework provides a normative bridge between the CPC formalism’s descriptive account of collective coherence and the practical demands of AI systems that genuinely serve human flourishing. Within CPC, the collective regularization term formalizes an analogous drive: agents are intrinsically motivated not merely to optimize individual utility, but to attend to others’ representations and negotiate shared understanding—embodying the relational ethic that care ethics demands.

Empirical support for this hypothesis is provided by Tennant et al. (2024, 2025), who formalize these ethical frameworks as intrinsic rewards and demonstrate that agents endowed with pro-social virtues can effectively “steer” selfish actors toward cooperative norms. Moreover, their application of multi-agent social outcome metrics—such as collective reward, Gini equality, and minimum payoff—provides the quantitative proxies necessary to evaluate the health of this co-creative process, ensuring that SA moves beyond mere prediction error.

Formalizing this connection would provide a philosophical foundation for defining “healthy democracy” and “care” in computational terms, moving beyond mere prediction error toward a richer conception of social flourishing.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed **SA via CPC** as a paradigm shift from unilateral control to mutual adaptation in human–AI ecosystems. We argued that the prevailing approach of constraining AI behavior through RL alone is insufficient for handling the complexity of symbol emergence and cultural evolution. To address this, we introduced the theoretical framework of **CPC**.

Our contributions can be summarized as follows:

1. **Redefining Alignment as Participation:** We reformulated the alignment problem not as maximizing a fixed reward function, but as minimizing **CFE** within a hybrid framework of “MARL + CPC.” This formulation mathematically captures the dual drive of intelligent agents: the pursuit of individual goals (MARL) and the intrinsic motivation to construct a shared reality (CPC).
2. **Incorporating Language and Culture:** Unlike standard MARL approaches that often lead to non-cooperative equilibria or fragmentation, our framework proposes to place the emergence of **symbol systems**—language and culture—at the core of alignment. We showed that the “collective regularization” term in CPC acts as the computational glue that binds diverse agents into a coherent society.
3. **Unifying Agent and Social Design:** We demonstrated that CPC provides a unified language for both the micro-level design of AI agents (e.g., co-creative learning, en-active noticing) and the macro-level design of social mechanisms (e.g., infrastructure for **digital democracy** and plurality).

For the ALife and the broader community, SA represents a return to the field’s roots: understanding intelligence as a phenomenon that emerges from the bottom up. However, it also marks a new direction—moving from observing “life as it could be” to actively cultivating “society as it should be co-evolved.”

We call upon the ALife community to engage in further theoretical and experimental research in this domain. The challenges of distinguishing “collaborative stability” from “coercive uniformity” to achieve **social homeostasis**, designing **plurality-preserving** “Haber-mas Machine” that facilitates genuine deliberation, and scaling these dynamics to global human–AI networks remain open. By embracing the role of “gardeners” rather than architects, we can steer the trajectory of our technological future away from a singular, fragile control toward a robust, flourishing plurality.

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A Glossary of Acronyms

The following table defines the acronyms used throughout this paper.

Table 2: List of acronyms used in this paper

Acronym	Full form
AGI	Artificial General Intelligence
ASI	Artificial Superintelligence
ALife	Artificial Life
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAIF	Collective Active Inference Framework
CFE	Collective Free Energy
CEFE	Collective Expected Free Energy
CPC	Collective Predictive Coding
DPO	Direct Preference Optimization
EFE	Expected Free Energy
FEP	Free Energy Principle
LLM	Large Language Model
MARL	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
MHNG	Metropolis-Hastings Naming Game
MUPI	EMbedded Universal Predictive Intelligence
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback
SA	Symbiotic Alignment
SES	Symbol Emergence System

B Summary of the Research Agenda

Table 3 summarizes the research agenda for SA via CPC discussed in Section 4.3, organized along three interrelated dimensions (theoretical foundations, architectural design, and evaluation), each comprising three concrete research directions.

Table 3: Summary of the research agenda for Symbiotic Alignment via CPC (Section 4.3).

Dimension	Research direction	Key CPC-based approach
Theoretical Foundations (from individual optimization to common ground)	(T1) Co-evolution of communication dynamics and network structure	Extend CPC beyond fully connected networks; model how the collective posterior may fragment into disconnected modes under CFE minimization.
	(T2) Semantic divergence and meaning fragmentation	Use SES theory to model how a shared symbol w is grounded in different internal states z across communities, deepening polarization.
	(T3) Affective polarization	Integrate interoceptive predictive coding into CPC to link persistent social prediction errors to allostatic load and entrenched fragmentation.
Architectural Design (implementing agents for SA)	(A1) Co-creative learning agents	Develop local update rules that approximate the gradient of the non-decomposable collective term; design decentralized coordination protocols for LLM agents.
	(A2) Mediator / bridging agents	Ground mediator systems (e.g., Habermas Machine) in CPC; map heterogeneous internal representations onto shared symbolic variables to lower energy barriers between worldviews.
	(A3) Grounded large-scale multi-agent simulation	Develop Sim-to-Real methodologies for social simulation; calibrate and validate against deliberation platforms (e.g., Polis/vTaiwan).
Evaluation (defining and measuring “good” alignment)	(E1) Whether CFE minimization yields desirable states	Examine optimization traps and capability asymmetries that may collapse plurality into a singular mode.
	(E2) Monitoring and visualizing collective inference	Develop tractable CFE approximations and visualization frameworks to detect fragmentation and measure multimodality of the collective posterior.
	(E3) Connection to ethical traditions	Relate CPC to relational care ethics and other ethical traditions; formalize ethical frameworks as intrinsic rewards and social-outcome metrics.